

CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Schools WG Maintenance Plan

For the year 2020

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The output of the CODATA-RDA Research Data Science School WG will be maintained by the CODATA-RDA Task Group Working Group. In particular a sub-group will review the curriculum on a regular basis (i.e. meeting virtually meeting at least once every six months to ensure that the materials are up to date and relevant. The members identified for this role are

Rob Quick, Raphael Cobé, Venkat Shanmugasundaram, Solomon Gizaw, Steve Diggs and Gail Clement-Peretsmann. Materials as updated will be regularly deposited onto Zenodo.